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IMPROVEMENT OF LEGISLATION IN THE FIELD OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

***Abstract:** This article discusses the issues of assessing the regulatory impact of regulatory legal acts in the field of intellectual property on the example of such an object of intellectual property as know-how.*

In the course of the study, the positive experience of foreign countries in this area was studied, relevant proposals were made to improve the current legislation.

***Keywords:** regulatory impact assessment, intellectual property, know-how, transfer of exclusive rights.*

The improvement of the legislative framework and the development of high-quality regulatory legal acts in the field of protection and protection of intellectual property objects is a priority direction of the ongoing reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of intellectual property.

Innovative technologies, being a key factor in the economy, stimulate the development of new methods of cost reduction using know-how. Recently, this term has been widely used. This is especially due to the popularization of the business environment.

The dictionary-reference "Intellectual Property" defines the term "know-how" as "confidential knowledge, including information of a technical, economic, administrative, financial nature, the use of which provides certain advantages to the person who received them."⁴⁰. Thus, know-how consists of knowledge that gives its rightholder advantages over other entrepreneurs, by virtue of its innovation.

The American legal system defines know-how as information that includes data on any formulas, devices, systematized information, computer programs, design developments, technologies and processes. These processes must have an independent economic value, actual or potential, due to the unknown or inaccessibility to other persons

⁴⁰ Интеллектуальная собственность: словарь-справочник / Под общ.ред. А.Д. Корчагина. - М., 1995. С. 90.

who may receive economic benefits from their disclosure or use. This means that in the American legal system, know-how is understood as information unknown to third parties that has material value for its rightholder. Also, the specified information should be the subject of reasonable efforts to keep them secret.

A more one-sided approach is applied in European law in relation to know-how. Technical information that is kept secret, is significant and can be identified in any acceptable way is considered as know-how. This approach is dictated by the objectives of the development and adoption of a document aimed at regulating the transfer of technologies, which are based on technical information⁴¹.

Thus, know-how refers to innovative ideas that have commercial value because they are unknown to others. In addition, in connection with these innovations, reasonable steps have been taken to preserve their confidentiality by the copyright holder.

According to Kolodeznikova M.V. and Glevich M.A. know-how (from Eng. know how — "know how")⁴² or the secret of production is information of any nature (production, technical, economic, organizational and others), including the results of intellectual activity in the scientific and technical field, as well as information about the methods of professional activity that have actual or potential commercial value due to their anonymity to third parties, to which third parties do not have free access on a legal basis and in respect of which the owner of such information has introduced a trade secret regime⁴³.

In the textbook on business law, I.A.Zenin formulates the concept of know-how as "unguarded confidential scientific, technical, commercial, financial and other information with commercial value, as well as various production skills and experience in their application, that is, information that exists only in its living carrier⁴⁴».

⁴¹ Мухамедшин И.С. Право на ноу-хау (секреты производства). С. 95.

⁴² Колодезникова М.В. Северо-Восточный федеральный университет имени М.К. Аммосова (СВФУ им. М.К. Аммосова) (Россия, г. Якутск) «НОУ-ХАУ В МЕДИЦИНЕ»// КиберЛенинка: научная электронная библиотека открытого доступа – [Электронный ресурс]. – Режим доступа: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/nou-hau-v-meditsine>

⁴³ Глевич М.А. Пермский государственный национальный исследовательский университет «К вопросу о соотношении понятий «секрет производства» и «коммерческая тайна»// КиберЛенинка: научная электронная библиотека открытого доступа – [Электронный ресурс]. – Режим доступа: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/k-voprosu-o-sootnoshenii-ponyatiy-sekret-proizvodstva-i-kommercheskaya-tayna>

⁴⁴ Зенин И.А. Предпринимательское право: учебник для вузов. - М., 2008. С. 406.

We agree with the opinions of Kolodeznikova M.V., Glevich M.A., regarding the fact that know-how, in other words, the secret of production can be information of any nature (production, financial, technical, economic, organizational) having commercial value; however, we cannot agree with the opinion of Zenin I.A. regarding the fact that know-how is unguarded information.

From the above, it can be concluded that know-how is confidential information about the results of intellectual activity in any field of activity, it can be industrial, financial, technical, economic, organizational sphere, which have commercial value for the owner. The owners of know-how can take measures to protect the secret of production, since the loss of confidentiality of information leads to the loss of the monopoly on know-how.

It should be noted that the legislative regulation of know-how in the Republic of Uzbekistan is reflected in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Article 42 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that everyone is guaranteed freedom of scientific and technical creativity⁴⁵.

Unfortunately, in the Republic of Uzbekistan there is no special law regulating the legal relations arising in the process of interaction of know-how.

However, these legal relations are more or less regulated by Chapter 64 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, although it is worth noting that in this chapter the know-how is given together with undisclosed information and only 3 articles are devoted to it.

On the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the unified policy on the protection of intellectual property objects is carried out by the Intellectual Property Department of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan, since the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, changes have been constantly made to the activities of this body, then we will consider how the structure of the organization has changed.

From 1991 to 2011, the sphere of intellectual activity in the Republic of Uzbekistan was regulated by two state bodies: the State Patent Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan,

⁴⁵ Конституция Республики Узбекистан от 08.12.1992 г. – [Электронный ресурс]. – Режим доступа: <https://lex.uz/docs/35869#41992>

as well as the Uzbek Republican Agency for Copyright.⁴⁶ The State Patent Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan implemented a unified state policy in the field of protection of industrial property objects. The State Patent Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan accepted applications for industrial property objects for consideration, conducted state scientific and technical expertise, state registration on them, issued security documents, issued an official bulletin, rules. The Uzbek Republican Copyright Agency was a public administration body specially authorized to solve problems in the field of copyright and related rights protection. The main tasks of the agency were:

- * Ensuring the implementation of a unified state policy in the field of copyright and related rights protection;

- * Registration of works of science, literature and art, as well as the authors of these works, keeping records of legal entities and individuals using objects of copyright and related rights on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

That is, in 1991-2011, there was no single state body in the field of intellectual property on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which led to the confusion of copyright holders when they applied for registration of an intellectual property object; to unnecessary costs in rule-making in order to issue numerous regulatory legal acts to regulate the activities of the two bodies.

The second stage of the development of this sphere in the Republic of Uzbekistan took place in 2011-2019, when the State Patent Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the Uzbek Republican Agency for Copyright, were united and the Intellectual Property Agency under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan was created.⁴⁷ But the activities of the Intellectual Property Agency under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan were found unsatisfactory in the legal protection of intellectual property and the implementation of generally recognized international norms, and the Intellectual Property Agency was transferred to the system of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 2019 to March 2022.

⁴⁶ Khujayev, S. A. (2018). Judgments under the law of the republic of uzbekistan «on banks and bank activity» in the new edition. *International Journal of Legal Studies (IJOLS)*, 4(2), 295-301.

⁴⁷ Мукумов Б. Перспективы развития модели «Умного регулирования» //Современные тенденции развития цифровизации в сфере юстиции. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 75-78.

The next stage of intellectual property development covers 2019-2022. In accordance with the Resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 01.07.2019 No. PP-4380 "On measures to organize the activities of the Agency for Intellectual Property under the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and dated 8.02.2019. No. PP-4168 "On measures to improve public administration in the field of intellectual property", the Intellectual Property Agency was transferred to the system of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with the recognition of its unsatisfactory activities for the legal protection of intellectual property and the implementation of generally recognized international norms. And as a result of these reforms, in 2018-2022, the Republic of Uzbekistan joined four international treaties in the field of intellectual activity, the number of patents and trademark certificates issued increased by 3.3 times than in previous years.

The innovations taking place in the field of intellectual property in recent days have also affected the structure of the Agency for Intellectual Property under the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In particular, according to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 03/17/2022 No. UP-89 "On measures to further improve the efficiency of the activities of bodies and institutions of justice in ensuring the rights and freedoms of citizens, as well as in the provision of legal services", the Intellectual Property Agency and its territorial centers, with the transfer of tasks, functions and powers were joined To the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In this regard, the positive experience of Great Britain on the subject under consideration attracts special attention. The State body that carries out regulatory regulation in the field of know-how is the Intellectual Property Agency, which is subordinate to the Ministry of Business, Innovation and Vocational Training.

It should be noted that the definition of the term know-how is contained in the UK Law "On Income and Taxes of Corporations" of 1970, which defines that know-how means any "industrial information, technical techniques that directly contribute to the

production of goods and materials, mining, chemical compounds, as well as during the agricultural and forestry work, or fishing⁴⁸».

In accordance with paragraph 5 of the Rules "On Production Secrets (Law Enforcement, etc.)" of the United Kingdom, the statute of limitations for applying to court in cases of illegal acquisition, use or disclosure of know-how is 6 years, and paragraph 6 of the Rules stipulates that the statute of limitations begins to flow from the moment when the owner of the know-how becomes aware of the illegal acquisition, use or disclosure of production secrets.

When comparing the above provision with the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it turned out that the current legislation, namely Chapter 64 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, does not disclose in detail the limitation period, but establishes liability for damages caused by the illegal use of know-how. The general statute of limitations, which is three years, will apply to cases of illegal acquisition, use or disclosure of know-how⁴⁹.

As can be seen, the rule regarding the limitation period is also provided for in the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. However, the statute of limitations under the legislation of the United Kingdom and the current legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan differ.

Disputes in the field of know-how in the UK are considered by the following judicial authorities:

- - Court for Intellectual Property of Enterprises (Court for Enterprises in the Field of Intellectual Property (IPEC);
- Court for the Consideration of Disputes Related to Copyright (Copyright Court);
- Patent Court (Patent Court), which is part of the High Court of Justice of England and Wales (High Court of England and Wales))⁵⁰. It is not difficult to notice that in this regard, the UK has moved much ahead of the Republic of Uzbekistan by creating courts specially authorized to consider intellectual disputes.

⁴⁸ <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1970/10/section/386/enacted>

⁴⁹ Гражданский Кодекс Республики Узбекистан (часть первая) от 21.12.1995 г. – [Электронный ресурс]. – Режим доступа: <https://lex.uz/docs/111181>

⁵⁰ Г.А. Гасымова, «ПРАВО НА НОУ-ХАУ В ВЕЛИКОБРИТАНИИ И США»// КиберЛенинка: научная электронная библиотека открытого доступа – [Электронный ресурс]. – Режим доступа: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/pravo-na-nou-hau-v-velikobritanii-i-ssha>

No less interesting is the experience of the United States of America in this area. In the United States, the government body directly responsible for regulatory regulation and coordination of work in the field of know-how is the U.S. Patent and Trademark Office, the United States Department of Commerce (U.S. Patent and Trademark Office), which performs control functions in the field of legal protection and use of know-how objects, develops and adopts departmental regulations, registers inventions, industrial designs, trademarks, breeding achievements and grants patents on the basis of applications from copyright holders, maintains the appropriate register)⁵¹.

In the United States of America, there is no definition of the concept of know-how in federal legislation. But the high value of know-how for entrepreneurs is confirmed by the description of the economic value of know-how for the use of this information in industry or trade in the model Unified Law on Trade Secrets. The Unified Law interprets the secret of production as a form of ownership, the right to which can be allocated or licensed, since it provides for liability for the appropriation of know-how by unscrupulous purchasers⁵².

In addition, in the United States, copyright relations on know-how are regulated by the Copyright Act of 1976 and the Digital Millennium Copyright Act of 1999.

At the same time, most US courts tend to understand the term "know-how" as classified technical information intended only for industrial purposes, which is of less importance than, for example, an invention.

The Supreme Court of the United States in the decision in the case of *Ruckelhaus v. Monsanto* noted that the right to secrecy of production is protected in accordance with the provisions on the inadmissibility of the seizure of private property, enshrined in the Fifth Amendment to the U.S. Constitution.⁵³

American legislation does not establish criminal liability for the misuse of production secrets, but these actions may be included in other crimes, such as theft.

⁵¹ Г.А. Гасымова, «ПРАВО НА НОУ-ХАУ В ВЕЛИКОБРИТАНИИ И США»// КиберЛенинка: научная электронная библиотека открытого доступа – [Электронный ресурс]. – Режим доступа: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/pravo-na-nou-hau-v-velikobritanii-i-ssha>

⁵² <https://www.wipo.int/edocs/lexdocs/laws/en/us/us034en.pdf>

⁵³ <https://supreme.justia.com/cases/federal/us/467/986/>

So, in the United States, the Law "On Economic Espionage" of 1996 is in force, and a person guilty of stealing know-how can be fined up to \$ 10 million or imprisoned for 15 years⁵⁴.

Considering an example of the application of this rule in law enforcement practice, it should be noted that in 1986-1990, Dr. Ronald Hoffman, a rocket engine designer and a leading researcher at the International Corporation of Applied Sciences (Science Applications International Corporation), sold one of the technologies prohibited for export to several foreign companies. Ronald Hoffman was convicted of economic espionage, because as a result of his actions, foreign companies made significant progress in the development of space technologies, which confirmed the value of know-how, despite the fact that there was no violation of the right to know-how and the technology was not made public.

Of particular interest is the experience of some countries of the European Union on the subject under consideration.

In Germany, the rules governing production secrets are contained in many regulations, of which the most important is the Law on Combating Unfair Competition (Act against Unfair Competition). Its rules apply to both the owner's employees and third parties. An employee is criminally liable both for disclosing production secrets to third parties and for using such information for purposes unrelated to the interests of the employer. After termination of the employment contract, the former employee is free to use the acquired knowledge and skills. At the same time, the use of information recorded in documents or otherwise, as well as that which the employee purposefully remembered for use after the termination of the employment contract, will be considered illegal⁵⁵.

Based on the comparative legal analysis of the legislations of foreign countries and the current legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it follows that the regulatory framework governing legal relations regarding know-how in foreign countries is more progressive and meets modern challenges.

Taking into account the positive experience of foreign countries, the following is proposed to improve the current legislation:

⁵⁴ <https://wipolex.wipo.int/ru/text/405984>

⁵⁵ <http://lexdigital.ru/2012/041/>

- to provide a definition of the term "know-how" in the current legislation, to designate its characteristics, according to which the attribution of certain confidential information to know-how is determined;

- to develop a special type of contract – a contract on the transfer of know-how, to provide in it all the conditions for keeping confidential information constituting a trade secret. To disclose in more detail in regulatory legal acts the procedure for concluding such an agreement on the transfer of rights to "know-how", to describe what conditions it should contain and what steps should be taken by the parties after this agreement is terminated;

- to create specialized courts that consider cases on disputes arising in the field of intellectual property;

- codify all regulatory legal acts in the field of intellectual property.

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